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IUAES

31 July 2025

WAU Leadership Statement on the 2025 WAU Congress

This is a statement on behalf of the WAU Leadership concerning the organization of the 2025 WAU Congress to be held in Antigua, Guatemala, 3-8 November 2025. Preparations for the Congress are well underway, thanks to the hard work of the Organizing Committee, chaired by Ricardo Fagoaga Hernández, and the Scientific Committee, chaired by Alejandra Letona Rodríguez. The authority of these committees, whose members include representatives from WAU leadership, along with the general framework for organizing the Congress, are set forth in a Memorandum of Understanding that was agreed to by the elected leadership of WAU and the Organizing Committee Chair in March 2025.

The WAU Leadership reaffirms its commitment to uphold the agreement, which, in simplified terms, authorizes the Organizing and Scientific Committees to determine the content of the Congress program and communications about the Congress. This includes the scholarly, social, and community engagement events on the program, and the amount of program space reserved for activities of the WAU extended governance network, i.e., the WAU Steering Committee, the IUAES Executive Committee, the IUAES Council of Commissions, the WCAA Organizing Committee, WCAA Task Forces, and the WCAA Delegates Symposium. The content of these governance-related activities at the Congress is the responsibility of the respective governance bodies.

Over the past several months, a number of disagreements have been brought to our attention. These disagreements have been dealt with informally in an attempt to de-escalate conflicts and avoid distracting from the important and challenging work of preparing for a global Congress, but we recognize there was a lack of formal procedural response in some cases. WAU leadership now takes this opportunity to offer a formal declaration: The framework and authorities that are spelled out in the MOU are indeed applicable to all. The MOU recognizes the ultimate authority on the WAU Steering Committee to determine the disposition of complaints concerning individual participants or Congress attendees about whom complaints have been registered, and the Congress Organizing Committee must work with the WAU Steering Committee to determine the disposition of these complaints. Neither the Congress Organizing Committee nor the WAU Steering Committee may act unilaterally.

Individual members of the extended WAU leadership network, whether acting on their own or in an official capacity, are expected to be familiar with the terms of this MOU and abide by them when representing the Congress and its program of events. When individuals, regardless of their intentions, act on behalf of the extended WAU governance network in a manner that is inconsistent with the letter and spirit of the MOU. WAU leadership will insist that they rectify their actions.

For example, on 5 May, the head of the Council of Commissions (CoC) tried to discredit the work of the Scientific Committee and overrule some of its decisions, which is inconsistent with the MOU. The CoC head was called out by WAU leadership as acting in a manner inconsistent with the MOU.

In addition, on July 11 a complaint was filed about the CoC 2024 Annual Report, which included information regarding panels in the 2025 WAU Congress and was posted before the official Congress program was completed, even though the CoC leaders were asked beforehand not to publish this information. The Annual Report was modified to note that the list of Commission-proposed panels is preliminary, and awaits approval of the final program.

The WAU leadership regrets this violation of the MOU and acknowledges that WAU 2025 Organizing Committee has full authority over the Congress program content as well as other official communications regarding the Congress. CoC leaders and Chairs will be instructed to seek the Organizing Committee's concurrence before sharing WAU 2025 Congress information in the future.

In another example, on 22 July a complaint was filed against a Commission Chair because they instructed CoC members to disregard emails or notifications sent to them by the WAU 2025 Congress, which violates the spirit of collaboration between WAU and the Congress. The WAU leadership will address this issue accordingly.

We have not found a provision that gives the Congress authority to unilaterally remove members from participating in the Congress. Therefore, as stated in the MOU, in the case of disagreements or misunderstandings concerning the Congress that arise on a matter not specified in the MOU such as the aforesaid one, both the Organizing Committee and the WAU shall make every effort to resolve the issue in the best interest of the WAU. At the same time, the WAU SC must insist that all members of the extended WAU Leadership network are familiar with and agree to abide by the framework set forth in the MOU.

Many individuals have volunteered a considerable amount of time in service to the WAU and to the 2025 Congress, for which we are deeply grateful, since without this voluntary service we could not function. It is in the best interest of the WAU to maintain a respectful, inclusive, and safe environment throughout the course of planning for and implementing the Congress. We call on everyone who is involved in planning for the Congress to focus their energies from this date forward on the Congress's success.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Gordon Mathews', with a long horizontal stroke extending to the right.

Gordon Mathews
Chair, WCAA
Co-Chair, WAU SC

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Virginia R. Dominguez', with a long horizontal stroke extending to the right.

Virginia R. Dominguez
Secretary General, IUAES
Acting Co-Chair, WAU SC